

Structural Analysis of Filament-Winding Pressure Vessels

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ABSTRACT

A method of finite element analysis is presented for stresses in axisymmetrically loaded filament winding pressure vessels. An analytic approach is developed to obtain the distributions of anisotropic elastic constants by use of lamination theory, and then the stiffness equation is derived for curved elements. The method is general and can handle arbitrary laminate construction with possible meridional variation in anisotropic properties of shell elements. The equations are given in form readily adaptable to a computer solution. Numerical results of the analysis are compared with values obtained from hydrostatic test of a filament-wound pressure vessel with a torispherical end closure.

